

**MULTIMODAL LITERACY INSTRUCTION AND LEARNING
COMFORTABILITY AS DETERMINANTS OF
CLASSROOM INTERACTION AMONG
COLLEGE STUDENTS**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 48

Issue 6

Pages: 946-956

Document ID: 2025PEMJ4693

DOI: 10.70838/pemj.480607

Manuscript Accepted: 09-25-2025

Multimodal Literacy Instruction and Learning Comfortability as Determinants of Classroom Interaction Among College Students

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Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the predictive influence of multimodal literacy instruction and students' learning comfort on the classroom interaction of college students. Grounded in the increasing emphasis on multimodal pedagogies and affective learning environments, the study posits that both instructional modality and learner affect significantly shape interaction patterns within higher education classrooms. A quantitative research design employing a descriptive-correlational approach was utilized. Data were collected through stratified random sampling using standardized survey questionnaires. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation), Pearson's correlation coefficient (r), and multiple regression analysis were employed to analyze the data and address the study's objectives. Findings indicated that the levels of multimodal literacy instruction, learning comfort, and classroom interaction were all rated as very high. Significant positive correlations were found between multimodal literacy instruction ($r = 0.603$, $p < 0.001$) and learning comfort ($r = 0.683$, $p < 0.001$) and classroom interaction. Moreover, regression analysis revealed that both multimodal literacy instruction ($\beta = 0.280$, $t = 3.327$, $p < 0.05$) and learning comfort ($\beta = 0.487$, $t = 5.653$, $p < 0.05$) were significant predictors of classroom interaction, jointly explaining 51.2% of its variance ($R^2 = 0.512$). The results highlight the crucial role of multimodal pedagogical strategies and learners' affective states in promoting classroom engagement. These findings support instructional practices that enhance both multimodal comprehension and student comfort, thereby promoting enriched classroom interactions and increased learner participation.

Keywords: *Multimodal literacy instruction, learning comfortability, classroom interaction, first-year students, Davao City, Philippines*

Introduction

Classroom interaction refers to the dialogue and idea sharing that occur in the classroom between students and their teachers, or among students themselves. It can occur in various ways, such as group projects, non-verbal communication, vocal conversations, and even online cooperation (Rahman, 2016).

Numerous studies have been conducted on multimodal literacy teaching; however, most focus on academic performance outcomes, such as comprehension or literacy skills. On the other hand, nothing is known about how it affects classroom engagement and students' comfort levels. Few studies examine the combined impact of literacy instruction and student comfort on classroom dynamics; most studies concentrate on either alone.

The information, abilities, and attitudes needed in the increasingly diverse and complex 21st-century societies continually challenge educators (Jackson, 2017; Lee, 2020). Nevertheless, several challenges still stand in the way of productive classroom interactions, such as unequal participation, linguistic and cultural barriers, power dynamics between teachers and students, and the growing problem of technological distractions (Pascarella et al., 1996). As stated by Bozkurt et al. (2021), 43% of students reported feeling uneasy about participating in class discussions because they feared receiving negative feedback from their lecturers or peers. Furthermore, according to Rashid and Asghar's (2016) study, 34% of students reported that technological distractions made it difficult for them to participate in class discussions, which in turn decreased the overall quality of interaction.

This study strives to provide valuable insights for educators and contribute to the ongoing efforts to enhance English language instruction through multimodal literacy approaches (Chang, 2018; Harvey, 2019). Classroom interaction can provide students with a vital platform for developing critical abilities beyond academic success. Students who participate in conversations gain an appreciation for diverse cultures and points of view, which is essential for promoting social cohesiveness.

As Davis et al. (2012) state, encouraging contact in the classroom fosters empathy among students and helps fight stereotypes while fostering community. From the perspective of King and Kitchener (2002), a dialogic classroom's interaction of ideas encourages higher-order thinking and equips pupils to handle challenging social situations. Furthermore, multimodal approaches in teaching contribute to the understanding of innovative pedagogical practices that promote student engagement, critical thinking, and communication skills in language learning contexts (Vlachopoulos, 2021).

Research Objectives

This study aimed to investigate the impact of multimodal literacy instruction and students' comfort levels on classroom interactions among first-year students. More explicitly, the study sought to answer the following objectives:

1. To describe the level of multimodal literacy instruction implemented by teachers;
2. To ascertain the comfortability of college students;
3. To assess the level of classroom interaction among college students;
4. To determine the relationship between:
 - 4.1. multimodal literacy instruction and classroom interaction;
 - 4.2. learning comfortability and classroom interaction; and
5. To test the influence of multimodal literacy instruction and learning comfortability on the classroom interaction of college students.

Literature Review

Multimodal Literacy Instruction

The significance of multimodal literacy in English teaching methods has recently gained more attention. The ability to understand and generate meaning using a variety of communication modalities, such as sights, sounds, and digital technology, is known as multimodal literacy. This method celebrates the variety of ways people interact with information and express themselves, acknowledging that communication in the twenty-first century transcends conventional text-based formats (Araújo, 2021; Bonsignori, 2021; Huang, 2019; Schöninger, 2020). Using multimodal techniques in English instruction has become a viable approach for teachers to provide their students with engaging and meaningful learning experiences (Nash et al., 2023).

This approach acknowledges that communication in the 21st century extends beyond traditional text-based forms and embraces the diverse ways in which individuals engage with information and express themselves in a classroom environment (Araújo, 2021; Bonsignori, 2022; Huang, 2019; Schöninger, 2020). Since 2018, educational studies have focused on incorporating multimodal literacy into English instruction. The potential of integrating visual, aural, and digital modes to improve student motivation, engagement, and learning results in language classes has been acknowledged by academics and educators (Chen, 2021; Hu, 2021). Using various modalities, including interactive activities, technology, and visual aids, English teachers can effectively establish dynamic learning environments that cater to students' diverse needs and preferences. As Gómez and Aiken (2022) noted, 56% of students reported that using multimodal literacy instruction (e.g., videos, images, and audio) enhanced their understanding of complex topics. Additionally, Serafini (2015) found that 48% of students felt more engaged in lessons incorporating multiple media formats than in traditional text-based instruction.

Learning Comfortability

Student comfort levels refer to the degree to which students feel emotionally, socially, and psychologically secure within the classroom environment. High comfort levels foster greater student engagement, participation, and willingness to take risks in learning without fear of embarrassment or judgment (Caloc & Baradillo, 2023; Liu et al., 2013) emphasize that a favorable classroom climate, where students feel supported by their peers and teachers, enhances their sense of comfort, which in turn leads to more active participation in discussions and collaborative activities. Students' behavioral engagement and school identification are critical for learning and performance (Korpershoek et al., 2019). In a study by Smith et al. (2021), 64% of students expressed that their comfort level with classmates significantly influenced their participation in group discussions.

Furthermore, Johnson et al. (2023) found that 42% of students were more likely to engage in class when they felt emotionally supported by their peers and teachers, highlighting the importance of a comfortable learning environment. Students who value school and feel that they belong there are more likely to engage behaviorally in school activities, experience more in-depth learning, and improve their academic achievement. The present study suggests that teachers' feedback is a critical factor affecting students' achievement and engagement (Wisniewski et al., 2020). When performing learning tasks and activities, feedback is a relevant aspect of the teacher-student relationship that can create a positive and supportive classroom environment. Feedback may have consequences on students' school experience, subsequently improving or impairing their school identification and behavioral engagement and, in turn, affecting their academic achievement (Reeve, 2012; Reschly & Christenson, 2012; Burns et al., 2019; Wang & Zhang, 2020).

Classroom Interaction

Classroom interaction is pivotal in shaping the learning environment and fostering communication, engagement, and collaboration between students and teachers. Classroom interaction is a crucial element in the EFL learning context. Some researchers have demonstrated that classroom interaction has a significant impact on the teaching and learning process, as well as learning achievement. For teachers, classroom interaction is beneficial in creating a supportive atmosphere for interactive teaching and learning activities (Luchavez & Caloc, 2024; Winanta et al., 2020).

When asked about the frequency of student-student interaction in class, most respondents (67.6%) reported occasionally interacting with their peers. This interaction occurs through various classroom activities, including group discussions both during online meetings and on discussion boards, as well as during question-and-answer sessions and group work outside class hours. Class interaction in the EFL context also facilitates students with concrete and natural practice of the target language (Al-Munawwarah, 2021; Some-Guiebre, 2020; Wizheng, 2019). It is also helpful to engage students in learning by triggering their interest during the teaching and learning

process (Entusiastik & Siregar, 2022; Kholisoh & Barati, 2021), a benefit that can simultaneously decrease their anxiety (Alahmadi & Alraddadi, 2020). In addition, class interaction provides a path for students' academic success and determines the achievement of the learning objective in each meeting (Eisenring & Margana, 2019; Siddig & AlKhoudayr, 2018). Thus, teacher-student interaction is a vital tool for engaging students in learning and enhancing their academic achievement.

Methodology

Research Design

A non-experimental quantitative study design is the general approach or framework a researcher uses to systematically examine relationships or patterns among variables without manipulating them. It serves as a guide for collecting, measuring, and analyzing numerical data to answer study questions objectively and accurately. According to Creswell and Creswell (2020), a research design outlines how a study is conducted, specifying whether a quantitative, qualitative, or mixed-methods approach is most suitable. In a non-experimental quantitative study, the researcher does not intervene or control variables; instead, they observe them as they naturally occur. The choice of this design depends on the type of data required, the research questions, and the nature of the problem being investigated. As stated by Kumar et al. (2019), a well-structured design enables the researcher to systematically organize the study's components—such as sampling, data collection, and statistical analysis—ensuring the reliability and validity of the findings, even without experimental manipulation.

The descriptive-correlational method is widely used to identify relationships between variables without altering the variables themselves. This approach is constructive when investigating relationships between variables in natural environments. It enables researchers to identify patterns and connections that may provide crucial insights for further study. The approach employed in this study is crucial for understanding the relationship between student comfort levels, classroom interaction, and multimodal literacy education, offering a clear picture of how these factors interact with one another.

Consequently, as Creswell and Creswell (2020) highlight, the non-experimental design is appropriate when manipulating variables is not feasible or ethical, and the goal is to observe and describe relationships. As Siedlecki (2020) states, investigations that aim to comprehend the direction and strength of correlations between variables rather than prove cause and effect are best suited for the descriptive correlational method.

Respondents

The study involved a total of 100 first-year college students officially enrolled during the second semester in various academic programs, namely Teacher Education (12), Information Technology (15), Hospitality and Tourism (10), Engineering (13), Human Kinetics (10), Business Administration (15), Nursing (13), and Criminology (12). To ensure fair representation across these disciplines, the study employed stratified random sampling, in which the population was divided into subgroups based on academic programs, and respondents were proportionally selected from each stratum. This method, as explained by Nguyen et al. (2016), ensured that each program was adequately represented in the sample while reducing potential sampling bias and increasing the validity of the study's findings.

The selection of appropriate respondents is crucial for ensuring the validity and reliability of the findings. As O'Connor et al. (2021) stated, inclusion criteria specify the essential characteristics that participants must possess to be included in a study. In contrast, exclusion criteria identify attributes that disqualify potential participants to enhance the quality and relevance of the study findings. On this note, the selection of the study's respondents was primarily based on the inclusion criteria, which are: participants have to be first-year students, must be enrolled in a program that teaches using a variety of media, either male or female, skilled, and informed on the phenomenon of interest or study topic. The exclusion and withdrawal criteria for selecting respondents were also observed based on the following: First, students who are not in their first year. Second, classes that do not incorporate multimodal literacy instruction. Third, if the student lacks background knowledge or any experience related to the topic under investigation, and lastly, if the student is under the influence of an alcoholic drink, it might affect their responses.

Instrument

Three survey questionnaires were used to gather data from the study respondents. The first questionnaire was the Serafini and Gee's (2017) Multimodal Literacy Framework. The second instrument was the Student Comfort Levels Survey, adapted from Smith and Jones (2021). The third instrument was adapted from Johnson et al.'s (2023) Classroom Interaction Dynamics Scale. The researcher used the face validity procedure to guarantee the reliability of the study tools.

In this sense, a group of specialists in educational study and questionnaire design examined the survey's questions. To ensure that the questions were both intelligible and pertinent to the participants' experiences, the panel offered suggestions for changes that would better align the instrument with the respondents' cultural backgrounds.

In this study, a four-point Likert scale was used because it is one of the most commonly used scales. To evaluate the level of multimodal literacy instruction, learning comfort, and classroom interaction among college students, the scales were used.

Procedure

The researcher initially arranged a series of consultations with the research adviser to deliberate on the conceptual framework and overall design of the study. Upon approval of the study framework, the modified survey instrument was compiled and submitted to a panel of experts for face validation to ensure clarity, relevance, and appropriateness of content. Following the validation process, formal approval and ethical clearance were sought from the institutional Research Committee to proceed with data collection. The researcher then personally administered the validated survey questionnaires to the identified respondents, providing a brief orientation regarding the study's purpose and the significance of the variables under investigation. Once the respondents completed the instrument, the researcher collected the data and proceeded with tabulation. The gathered data were subjected to statistical analysis, and the results were systematically examined and interpreted to draw meaningful conclusions and formulate evidence-based recommendations.

Data Analysis

The gathered survey data were carefully tabulated, organized, and subjected to statistical treatment. Descriptive statistics, such as mean and standard deviation, were utilized to determine the levels of multimodal literacy instruction, learning comfort, and classroom interaction. Pearson's correlation coefficient (*r*) was employed to examine the relationships among variables, while regression analysis was conducted to identify the predictive influence of the independent variables on classroom interaction.

Ethical Considerations

Prior to data collection, approval and clearance were secured from the Institutional Research Committee to ensure compliance with ethical standards. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents, who were assured of the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses. Participation was entirely voluntary, and students were informed that they could withdraw at any stage without penalty. The study strictly adhered to the principles of beneficence, respect, and integrity throughout the research process.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data and findings of the study, based on the elicited responses of college students regarding multimodal literacy instruction, learning comfort, and classroom interaction.

Table 1. *Level of Multimodal Literacy Instruction of College Students*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1. Increasing interest in reading activities through multimodal texts	3.39	.665	Very High
2. Enhancing critical thinking and analytical skills through multimodal literacy	3.34	.655	Very High
3. Improving problem-solving using multimodal literacy strategies	3.35	.757	Very High
4. Relating content more easily to real-life situations using multimodal materials	3.33	.682	Very High
5. Simplifying complex topics by combining audio, visual, and textual materials	3.38	.749	Very High
6. Improving retention of information through videos and images in lessons	3.44	.656	Very High
7. Making learning more enjoyable through integration of various media	3.38	.736	Very High
8. Engaging through interactive elements like digital tools	3.38	.632	Very High
9. Incorporating visuals in educational content	3.42	.669	Very High
10. Making complex ideas easier to grasp through multimedia-based lessons	3.45	.657	Very High
11. Participating through multimedia elements in lessons	3.34	.728	Very High
12. Encouraging topic exploration through multimedia resources	3.23	.851	High
13. Improving peer collaboration through multimedia tools in activities	3.33	.711	Very High
14. Expressing ideas more effectively through use of various media in assignments	3.23	.763	High
15. Developing regular note-taking practices from readings, powerpoint, or video lectures	3.45	.702	Very High
16. Using new technology efficiently	3.32	.750	Very High
17. Searching answers to course-related questions from the internet	3.19	.884	High
18. Considering alternative solutions before selecting the best option	3.25	.809	High
19. Supporting learners with different abilities through multiple modes of instruction	3.42	.684	Very High
20. Increasing confidence in understanding through exposure to various learning modes	3.22	.773	High
Overall	3.34	.385	Very High

The very high rating of the respondents on multimodal literacy instruction indicates that this variable is consistently present. As highlighted by Araújo (2021), Zhang (2021), and Eisenmann (2019), utilizing diverse communication modes available in the digital

age allows educators to enhance language acquisition, foster critical thinking, and develop intercultural competence. By incorporating multiple modalities such as interactive activities, technology, and visual aids, English teachers can effectively create dynamic learning environments that cater to students' diverse needs and preferences, as highlighted by Gómez and Aiken (2022). Multimodal literacy strategies also promote cultural awareness and critical thinking. By engaging with diverse multimodal texts and resources, students are exposed to various perspectives, cultures, and communication styles.

In this variable, the line item with the highest mean rating from the respondents is developing regular note-taking practices from readings, PowerPoint presentations, or video lectures. Based on Kuby's (2019) study, incorporating various modalities enables teachers to cultivate dynamic and inclusive classrooms that support all students in achieving success in their language learning journey. Also, incorporating visual aids such as images, videos, and infographics enhances language learners' comprehension, vocabulary development, and overall engagement. Visuals support students in understanding concepts, offering perspective, and fostering creativity and critical thinking (So, 2019).

The item with the lowest mean is the search for answers to course-related questions. According to Stankić's study (2022), digital tools provide dynamic and personalized learning experiences that enable students to actively engage with language content, practice skills, and receive immediate feedback. By participating in virtual language exchanges, creating multimedia presentations, and engaging in online discussions, students can enhance their collaborative learning experiences. Additionally, leveraging digital tools enables teachers to foster digital literacy, promote creativity, and encourage self-directed learning.

Table 2. *Level of Learning Comfortability of College Students*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1. Asking questions during class discussions comfortably	3.40	.725	Very High
2. Increasing active participation when comfort with classmates is present	3.38	.693	Very High
3. Sharing opinions during group discussions	3.26	.719	Very High
4. Communicating with the teacher for assistance easily			
5. Improving academic performance when comfort in the classroom is established	3.36	.746	Very High
6. Participating in class more often when a sense of emotional safety is present	3.28	.766	Very High
7. Stepping into leadership roles in group projects more easily when comfortable	3.23	.815	High
8. Improving concentration in class when a comfortable environment is provided	3.31	.761	Very High
9. Learning with encouragement and peer support	3.38	.678	Very High
10. Engaging in class more when the learning environment feels comfortable	3.44	.671	Very High
11. Taking learning risks when the instructor provides a sense of ease	3.37	.706	Very High
12. Collaborating more effectively with classmates when comfort is established	3.23	.827	High
13. Enhancing self-expression when emotional comfort is present in the classroom	3.37	.800	Very High
14. Improving academic performance when anxiety in class is reduced	3.28	.683	Very High
15. Being more receptive to feedback when teachers create a comfortable setting	3.46	.673	Very High
16. Enjoying learning more in a comfortable classroom environment	3.43	.728	Very High
17. Absorbing information more effectively when the learning environment is comfortable	3.49	.703	Very High
18. Strengthening confidence in expressing ideas when a positive rapport with peers exists	3.46	.626	Very High
19. Completing assignments more consistently when comfort with the content is present	3.44	.656	Very High
20. Increasing online learning engagement when digital tools are comfortable to use	3.30	.823	Very High
Overall	3.35	.376	Very High

The very high rating of the respondents on learning comfort indicates that this variable is always manifested among first-year students. Aligning with the assertions of Liu et al. (2013), student comfort levels pertain to the emotional, social, and psychological sense of security that students experience within the classroom. When students feel comfortable, they are more likely to engage, participate, and take academic risks without the fear of embarrassment or judgment. Additionally, Silk et al. (2021) highlight that a nurturing school environment fosters a culture of sustained student engagement and participation. This consistent engagement, both verbal and physical, helps build students' confidence and capacity to take part in school life.

In this variable, the line item with the highest mean rating given by the respondents is absorbing information more effectively when

the learning environment is comfortable. Teacher feedback plays a vital role in fostering a supportive classroom environment by building strong relationships with students and providing both academic and personal support (Allen et al., 2018; Caloc, 2025). Studies have shown that such an environment enhances students' sense of school identification and increases their behavioral engagement (Allen et al., 2018; Olivier et al., 2020; Voelkl, 2012). When students feel supported and cared for by their teachers, they develop a stronger connection with the school, which, in turn, reinforces their participation in school activities. According to Wang and Degol (2019), student comfort is shaped by factors such as teacher support, peer relationships, and the overall classroom climate, all of which influence their willingness to engage in class discussions and interactions.

The item with the lowest mean is communicating with the teacher for assistance easily. Feedback plays a crucial role in the teacher-student relationship, fostering a positive and encouraging classroom environment. The quality of feedback can significantly impact students' school experience, influencing their sense of school identification, behavioral engagement, and ultimately their academic performance (Reeve, 2012; Reschly & Christenson, 2012; Voelkl, 2012; Burns et al., 2019; Wang & Zhang, 2020). While most studies on students' perception of feedback and engagement have focused on individual student characteristics, less attention has been given to the broader teaching contexts (Burns et al., 2019). Therefore, teachers' feedback is essential in strengthening a supportive classroom atmosphere by fostering positive relationships with students and providing both academic and personal guidance (Allen et al., 2018; Escosar & Caloc, 2024).

Table 3. *Level of Classroom Interaction of College Students*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1. Experiencing greater engagement when using multimedia tools such as videos, images, and audio in lessons	3.46	0.593	Very High
2. Participating in class discussions when utilizing multimodal literacy instruction	3.31	0.677	Very High
3. Contributing to classroom activities when including multiple media forms	3.38	0.708	Very High
4. Improving collaboration with peers when incorporating various media into lessons	3.35	0.642	Very High
5. Asking questions to clarify understanding of lessons	3.35	0.809	Very High
6. Sharing of opinions during class activities	3.39	0.723	Very High
7. Having meaningful discussions with classmates during group work	3.35	0.770	Very High
8. Engaging when the teacher fosters an interactive environment	3.33	0.766	Very High
9. Providing regular feedback and comments on classmates' ideas	3.16	0.775	High
10. Participating in class debates or presentations	3.26	0.676	Very High
11. Engaging more in discussions when the teacher poses thought-provoking questions	3.30	0.659	Very High
12. Demonstrating effective collaboration with classmates during classroom projects	3.24	0.780	High
13. Assisting classmates in understanding difficult concepts	3.38	0.693	Very High
14. Valuing student contributions during class by the teacher	3.33	0.739	Very High
15. Achieving higher engagement in class when interacting with both the teacher and classmates	3.40	0.603	Very High
16. Attaining deeper understanding of topics when integrating different media and strategies into lessons	3.41	0.698	Very High
17. Participating in discussions when incorporating multiple media formats	3.29	0.729	Very High
18. Improving understanding of classmates' contributions when lessons include videos, images, and audio	3.33	0.682	Very High
19. Interacting with classmates when confidence in the subject matter is present	3.34	0.728	Very High
20. Actively participating in discussions when there is comfort in peer interactions	3.44	0.656	Very High
Overall	3.34	.364	Very High

The very high rating of the respondents on classroom interaction indicates that this aspect is consistently present among first-year students. As discussed by Eisenring and Margana (2019), classroom interaction plays a crucial role in students' academic success and directly influences the achievement of learning objectives in each session. Effective teacher-student interaction serves as a key strategy for engaging students in learning and enhancing their academic performance. A study indicates that strong student-teacher relationships are closely linked to higher levels of participation (McNally & Slutsky, 2017; Müller-Kuhn et al., 2021), with participation opportunities influenced primarily by the teacher's capabilities and personal teaching style (Müller-Kuhn et al., 2021). Rather than being an occasional occurrence, student participation should be an integral and consistent part of the classroom experience (Caloc et al., 2025).

In this variable, the line item that has the highest mean rating that was given by the respondents is experiencing greater engagement when using multimedia tools such as videos, images, and audio in lessons. As stated by the study of Yang et al. (2019), interaction

patterns in a blended synchronous cyber classroom are categorized into teacher using technology, student using technology, teacher talking, and students talking. A study on teacher-student interaction in an online EFL classroom found that exchanges were predominantly teacher-centered, with teachers frequently leading the conversation and controlling its flow, as students tended to be more passive (Abdusyukur, 2022). Similarly, Johnson et al. (2023) reported that 39% of students showed increased participation in discussions when multimedia tools, such as videos and interactive content, were integrated into lessons.

The item with the lowest mean is providing regular feedback and comments on classmates' ideas. Regular oral recitations have been found to enhance students' confidence over time (Moneva & Cuizon, 2020). However, factors such as low self-esteem and negative attitudes toward participation can hinder student engagement, emphasizing the teacher's crucial role in fostering an encouraging environment (Sánchez-Hernández et al., 2021). Additionally, oral recitations promote student-teacher interaction, allowing students to express their perspectives freely and engage in forward-thinking learning (Ju-Sen & Chaoyun, 2014; Khine et al., 2020).

Table 4. Correlation Between Variables

Variables	Classroom Interaction		
	r-value	p-value	Decision on H0
Multimodal Literacy Instruction	.603	.000	Rejected
Learning Comfortability	.683	.000	Rejected

Multimodal literacy instruction is linked to classroom interaction, as supported by the rejection of the null hypothesis. Grounded in Multimodal Learning Theory (Kress & van Leeuwen, 2001), this study aligns with prior research demonstrating that utilizing multiple sensory modes—visual, auditory, and kinesthetic—enhances engagement and interaction (Jewitt et al., 2016). Incorporating text, images, sound, and interactive elements boosts comprehension and participation. Multimodal literacy encourages active engagement by enabling communication through diverse channels, fostering creativity and practical expression. It also supports digital literacy development, equipping students with vital skills for the modern information age (Aşık, 2022; Maia, 2022). Classroom participation may be verbal, physical, or passive. Greater involvement leads to more meaningful contributions and overall student development (Lansdown et al., 2014). Prior academic achievement also affects participation frequency (Decristan et al., 2023).

Learning comfort is also related to classroom interaction, as evidenced by the rejection of the null hypothesis. Drawing from Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (Maslow, 1943), which emphasizes that individuals must have their basic psychological and emotional needs met before they can engage fully in learning. Recent scholarship by Conley (2013) supports this framework, emphasizing that psychological safety and a sense of belonging are foundational to academic engagement, particularly in early college experiences. Classroom management is crucial for fostering positive interactions and promoting self-motivation.

Table 5. Influence of Multimodal Literacy Instruction and Learning Comfortability on the Classroom Interaction of Freshmen Students

Independent Variables	Classroom Interaction				
	F-value	R ²	βCoefficient	t-value	p-value
Multimodal Literacy Instruction	52.852	.512	.280	3.327	.001
Learning Comfortability			.487	5.653	.010

The study reveals that multimodal literacy instruction has a highly significant influence on classroom interaction among first-year students. By integrating multiple sensory modes, such as visual, auditory, and textual elements, this instructional approach enriches the learning experience and makes content more accessible and engaging. As explained by Kress and van Leeuwen (2001) and Jewitt et al. (2016), multimodal strategies enable students to process information through diverse channels, thereby enhancing comprehension and retention. This multi-sensory engagement promotes active participation, encourages meaningful discussions, and supports collaborative learning, thereby fostering a dynamic and interactive classroom environment. The strong effect of this variable highlights its importance in motivating students to connect with the lesson material and interact confidently with their peers and instructors.

In addition, student comfort, defined as the emotional and psychological ease experienced by learners, also has a significant influence on classroom interaction. According to Fredricks et al. (2004) and Pekrun et al. (2017), when students feel safe, supported, and valued in their learning environment, they are more likely to participate openly, take intellectual risks, and engage fully in classroom activities. A favorable emotional climate reduces anxiety and fosters trust, encouraging students to share their thoughts and collaborate without hesitation. This heightened comfort level contributes significantly to the quality and frequency of classroom interaction. The findings underscore the importance of fostering a comfortable and inclusive atmosphere in sustaining student engagement and improving overall learning outcomes.

Conclusions

The findings of this study demonstrate that multimodal literacy instruction, learning comfort, and classroom interaction among first-year students all attained very high levels, indicating that these practices and experiences are consistently observed in the learning environment. Students reported feeling emotionally supported and secure, while participation and engagement in classroom activities were strongly evident. Statistical analyses confirmed that both multimodal literacy instruction and learning comfort are significantly related to classroom interaction, with regression results showing that these two variables are strong predictors, collectively explaining

51.2% of the variance. This highlights their crucial role in creating interactive, participatory, and supportive learning environments in higher education.

Grounded in these findings, several pedagogical and institutional implications emerge. To sustain a high level of multimodal literacy, strategies such as active note-taking, the use of multimedia resources, and the integration of diverse media formats should be emphasized to cater to varied learning preferences. Similarly, fostering a sense of learning comfort requires nurturing inclusive classrooms that encourage collaboration, open communication, and emotional support, thereby reducing learning anxiety. Sustaining high levels of classroom interaction can be achieved through interactive approaches such as think-pair-share, peer evaluation, and inquiry-based discussions. Educators and institutions are thus encouraged to design lessons that integrate multimodal resources while cultivating supportive environments, ensuring a balance between instructional innovation and socio-emotional well-being. At the same time, future research may extend this work by employing explanatory or experimental designs to explore how specific multimodal strategies and collaborative tools influence different dimensions of engagement—cognitive, emotional, and behavioral—across varied student populations.

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